

KEEPING DIET AND HEALTHY FOOD

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Abstract: The article concentrates on a healthy diet and its importance as well as impact on overall well-being of the human's life. Keeping healthy diet regularly protects us from many dangerous diseases and malnutrition process. Such as diabets, cancer and heart disease.

Keywords: Obesity, diet, health, food, physical fitness.

In this developed era, the number of the artificial components rapidly increasing which is causing serious damage to our life. Diet involves over time, being influenced by many factors and complex interactions. Income, food prices (which will affect the availability and affordability of healthy foods), individual preferences and beliefs, cultural traditions, as well as geographical, environmental, social and economic factors all interact in a complex manner to shape individual dietary patterns. Therefore, promoting a healthy food environment, which promotes a diversified, balanced and healthy diet, requires involvement across multiple sectors and stakeholders, including government and the private sector, while safeguarding public health against vested interests.

Governments have a central role in creating a healthy food environment that enables people to adopt and maintain healthy dietary practices. [1,16]

“It is hard matter, my fellow citizens, to argue with belly, since it has no ears”.-
Cato the Elder, Roman senator and historian

Nowadays, because of the hectic life style, majority of the people are not following healthy diet and facing serious health problems. For the first time in human history, obesity is a bigger health crisis globally than hunger. More people alive today will suffer disability as a result of consuming excess calories than as a result of consuming too few. This stunning fact speaks volumes about the modern dietary dilemma. That's not to say hunger is no longer an issue in many areas of

our planet , but it's striking that even in the developing world, a growing number of people now suffer the consequences of eating too much of the wrong kinds of food. And this shift has happened within the lifetimes of most people reading this book [2,30].

Good food is one of life's greatest pleasures. The anticipation of a favorite meal; the first taste of a tender, perfectly prepared dish; the subtle flavors of herbs; the warmth and camaraderie of breaking bread with those we love; the feeling of fullness when all is done. The human palate is an extraordinary gift; its thousands of taste buds deliver myriad pleasurable sensations and inspire the human race's unrivaled culinary creativity [2,126].

Physical fitness is good bodily health; it is the result of regular exercise, proper diet and nutrition and proper rest for physical recovery. The term physical fitness is used in two ways: general fitness (a state of health and well-being) and specific fitness (a task-oriented definition based on the ability to perform specific aspects of sports or occupations). Physical fitness is the capacity of heart, blood vessels, lungs, and muscles to function at optimal efficiency. Earlier, fitness was defined as the capacity to carry out the day's activities without undue fatigue. Automation, increased leisure time, and changes in lifestyles following the Industrial Revolution meant that this criterion was no longer sufficient [4,4].

In summary, our technological world has greatly changed our life style, especially our routine of keeping diet. Therefore it is causing several health issues. Keeping healthy diet and consuming more organic food will be the best solution to these illness.

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